

THE IMPORTANCE OF MUSIC

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Abstract. *This article discusses the importance of music in education.*

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The lesson is a leading factor in the system of music education. Because music lessons cover children comprehensively. Music has a great positive effect on the mental and moral development of a child. Therefore, music lessons are called, first of all, educational lessons. The name of the subject is not only the methodology of music teaching, but also the methodology of music education. In order to teach lessons in the content of the new program, a music teacher must improve his musical and theoretical knowledge. Today, music plays an important role in the formation of a person, actively influences his emotions and psyche. One of the main tasks of secondary schools is to introduce students to the world of refinement and provide spiritual education. In this case, the teacher introduces the children to a certain piece of music, performs it expressively, "lively", attracts the attention of the students, improves their speech, expands their thinking ability, worldview, and actively affects emotional feelings.

The content of music lessons includes not only mastering, but also developing the attitude of the students' minds to reality, forming their aesthetic culture, and forming other inner feelings. The teacher's creative approach to the lesson is of great importance and sets a number of tasks: to develop new methods and tools in music education; to express the inextricable link between life and art.

To achieve these goals, the teacher must undergo serious preparation, work tirelessly on himself, that is, to improve the level of knowledge, he must visit scientific literature, new programs, fiction, theater, museums and improve the ways of raising consciousness (learning). An important role is played by the fact that the classroom where music lessons are held is tastefully furnished. It should be equipped with technical equipment, methodological visual aids, a piano and Uzbek folk instruments, and it should be conducted using new technology, using new programs, lesson plans and outlines. Thus, the purpose and content of all activities of music lessons should illuminate the lesson, connect it with life, and carry out all parts of the lesson in an integrated manner. A music lesson is distinguished from other lessons by its artistry, interest, and the fact that it arouses more creative pleasure, emotional feelings and figurative experiences in children. Therefore, a music lesson is, first and foremost, an educational lesson.

Music lessons differ from other lessons in the following specific features:

1. Five types of activities related to music theory and performance: vocal-choral lessons, music literacy, listening to music, playing children's musical instruments, and performing rhythmic movements.
2. Music differs from other art forms in its means of expression, that is, its "language" (melody, pitch, dynamic signs, tempo, alteration signs, intervals). If fiction is expressed in words, visual art in colors, and dance movements, then music is expressed in the melody created by musical sounds. If we perceive the above art forms through sight and hearing, we express music

only by listening to it with our ears, which is why even blind people have become accomplished musicians.

3. Music is an art form defined by a clear time scale. Therefore, if we do not tune in to the tempo of the music being performed and listen carefully to each of its elements, we cannot fully perceive the piece. When we listen to a classic piece over and over again, we feel its new artistic features. Music has a clear time scale.

4. Music has an active emotional effect on children, delights them, and provides creative experiences awakens. Children relax and receive artistic nourishment from good, meaningful, and interesting music lessons. They become lively, cheerful, and happy.

Also, music lessons are closely related to other subjects. Fine arts, literature, native language, mathematics, history, pedagogy, psychology, vocals, rhythmic, etc. These help to connect music lessons with life, to make the lesson meaningful and interesting. Music lessons also differ from other subjects in their mixed type of lesson.

In primary grades, a music lesson consists of five types of activities:

1. Singing in a choir.
2. Music literacy.
3. Listening to music.
4. Performing movements to music.
5. Children playing musical instruments

In the process of music culture lessons, music literacy is used to carry out artistic study and performance of musical works in the process of independent lesson activities on the basis of literacy. The content of music literacy gradually shapes students and gradually expands and deepens their circle of knowledge. Thus, it fulfills the educational function of a music literacy lesson. The main basis and pedagogical goal of musical literacy (activity), the quarterly topics given under the new program are implemented through competent analysis of works on singing and listening.

They are taught based on the impressions and musical experiences of students from their daily lives. Musical literacy is taught in the following stages:

1. To train children's attention to musical means of expression - melody, register, tempo, rhythm, dynamic signs.
2. To teach them to follow the rules of voice tuning and singing, to clap and play musical instruments.
3. Music creators: "composer", "performer", "listener" The content of the topic and information about the authors of the studied work is carried out through music literacy.

Listening to music is a key factor in music culture lessons. Because the sound of music is consciously perceived, its character and content are mastered. Based on the life experiences of students, certain feelings and thoughts are reflected in the core of each musical work. No matter what activity of the music lesson we take, it begins with listening to music, the perception of music begins and affects the psyche of students, therefore listening to music is considered the leading activity of the lesson. Each musical work listened to in the lesson depends on the content of the lesson from an artistic and ideological point of view and adheres to the principles of scientificity, continuity, and consistency.

Listening to music is carried out in several stages:

1. Attracting students' attention to the musical work and the teacher's introduction.
2. Listening to the work performed by the teacher or on a magnetic recording.
3. Simple analysis of the work in terms of musical and artistic-semantic aspects through a conversation.
4. Listening to the work again in its entirety and conducting a final conversation about the general impressions of the students about the work.

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